

Searching devices, new discoveries, and issues related to them in Estonian archaeology in 2020

Tuuli Kurisoo

Tallinna Ülikool, humanitaarteaduste instituut (Tallinn University, School of Humanities), Narva mnt 25, 10120 Tallinn, Estonia; tuuli.kurisoo@tlu.ee

Riina Rammo

Tartu Ülikool, ajaloo ja arheoloogia instituut, arheoloogia osakond (University of Tartu, Institute of History and Archaeology, Department of Archaeology), Jakobi 2, 51005 Tartu, Estonia

Maria Smirnova and Nele Kangert

Muinsuskaitseamet (National Heritage Board), Pikk 2, 10123 Tallinn, Estonia

INTRODUCTION

The main aims of this paper are twofold. First is to summarise recent contributions of users of searching devices and the public (Table 1, Fig. 1). The second objective is to address current problems that are related to the usage of metal detectors in Estonia. In 2020, 493 permits were issued by the National Heritage Board (hereafter MA) for the licenced hobby searchers. This number, however, does not reflect an exceptionally rapid growth of interest, but is caused by the changes in the new Heritage Conservation Act which took effect in May 2019 (see Kadakas 2020; Kurisoo *et al.* 2020, 270). As a result of the new law, many previously issued permits expired on 31 December 2019 and were replaced with new permits in 2020. Altogether 631 individuals held a valid licence in 2020, which is 14 individuals more than the year before (Kurisoo *et al.* 2020, 263).

Table 1 summarises the information about new discoveries and is used as a base for the overview of finds and find spots. It should be noted that the dataset includes all finds that reached the MA in 2020 regardless of the time of the actual discovery, but some deliberate exclusions have been made for better clarity of the data. For example, unidentified artefacts and assemblages of finds that originate from the 19th–20th centuries were left out. Also, most of the single finds were excluded from the dataset and only rare or otherwise noteworthy single artefacts are listed in the Table. Most of the finds discussed were found by using metal detectors and only two objects were found by chance (Table 1, nos 8, 216). The article follows the new chronology that was published in the new general treatment of Estonian prehistory in 2020 (Kriiska *et al.* 2020, fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Finds and sites discovered by users of searching devices or by the public in 2020.

Jn 1. 2020. a otsinguvahendiga ja juhulikult avastatud muistised ja leiud.

Administrative and settlement units: Estonian Land Board / haldusjaotus: Maa-amet (01.10.2021)

Map / Kaart: Tuuli Kurisoo

NORTHERN PARTS OF ESTONIA (HARJU, IDA-VIRU, JÄRVA, LÄÄNE-VIRU, AND RAPLA COUNTIES)

Approximately 60 percent of the scheduled find spots associate with northern parts of Estonia (Table 1; Fig. 1). The majority of these are located in Harju County (54 find spots). The number of reported sites and finds from Lääne-Viru County (34 find spots) exceeds previous years notably. Several discoveries in Lääne-Viru were made long ago, which explains the high number of records in Table 1. The search activity in Ida-Viru (22 find spots) and Järva (17 find spots) is comparable with 2019, but more discoveries (11 find spots) are reported from Rapla County than before.

According to current knowledge, most of the detector finds from the northern parts of Estonia are regarded as stray finds and approximately 35 percent of sites could be associated with an archaeological context, however, several of them with some doubt. The number of burial grounds is relatively high and they have been found in every county in northern Estonia. The earliest burials are dated to the Roman Iron Age (50–450 AD) (e.g. nos 34, 57, 60, 122, 123) but Final Iron Age (1050–1225 AD) cremations dominate among the studied sites (e.g. nos 3, 12, 17, 24, 30, 34, 56, 57, 128, 130, 135, 165, 171).

Most of the finds from the Final Iron Age burial sites represent widespread types of local ornaments and dress accessories such as bracelets, dress pins, brooches, strap ends etc. However, each year hobby searchers discover some rare artefacts. One such example comes from Mõdriku (no 132), where a copper alloy pendant with a Nordic ornament (Fig. 2), a unique find in Estonian context was collected. Mõdriku specimen belongs to Callmer's type

A3, which can be dated from the mid-10th century to the end of 10th century (Callmer 1989). Such pendants were made and used not only in Scandinavia, but also in Russia, where they were used over a longer period and more form variations are known (see more in Dementyeva 2007). Another unique ornament is a fragment of a silver bow brooch with zoomorphic decoration indicating probably a Migration Period or Pre-Viking Age burial site in Kiia (no 12), especially considering the finds of similar date collected there earlier (Rammo *et al.* 2017, table 1: 7).

Two coin hoards, of which one dates from the Viking Age (no 21) and the other from Early Modern period (no 136) were discovered from Harju and Lääne-Viru Counties. Additionally, a Final Iron Age jewellery deposit was unearthed in a former wetland area in Valingu (no 49). The Valingu find includes various items such as a chain arrangement, pendants, metal parts of knife sheaths, which along with tin mounts and spiral tubes for decorating textiles, form a set of clothing items and ornaments common to women in the North Estonian coastal region at the end of prehistory (Rammo 2020a). It remains unclear why the ornament set was deposited in the wetland, relatively far from the settlement. Interesting find assemblage from Jägala (no 7), a possible hoard that was already found in 2016, but handed over to the MA in 2020, should also be mentioned. It contains three types of large pewter beads that imitate large and hollow silver beads (Posti 2021). The latter were common jewellery worn by the local peasant women in the post-medieval times (Reidla 2012, 62–63). Additionally, a possible sacrificial place was discovered near Maardu (no 22; Rammo 2021). Various ornaments from the Migration Period until the Final Iron Age were collected from the drained wetland used as arable land nowadays. Fragments of nine scythes or sickles (Allikjärve, no 98) dating probably from the end of the prehistory or the beginning of the Middle Ages according to the estimations of Ain Mäesalu (TÜ) and Jüri Peets (TLU) could also indicate a deliberate deposit.

Generally, most of the settlement sites that are discovered by hobby searchers can be dated to the Modern Period (e.g. nos 39, 124) or their usage extends from the end of the prehistory to the Modern Period (e.g. nos 26, 100). Collected finds include various objects from coins to dress accessories (e.g., brooches, belt fittings, buttons). Long-term usage of dwelling sites is characteristic for many known settlement sites in Estonia. As the amount and diversity of material culture grows over time and the population also expands, Early Modern and Modern Period metal artefacts often predominate in the assemblages of finds. Moreover, it may be possible that many discoveries marked as stray finds in Table 1 refer to settlements, but it is difficult to draw conclusions about the nature of these sites on the basis of the preliminary data available to the authors of this paper.

Also several remarkable stray finds were handed over to MA and two of them are dated to the Stone Age. A copper adze was found from Tallinn (no 43) from an artificially heaped-up berm that had served as a terrace for a road. It turned out to be the oldest metal object recorded in Estonia with a 4000–2000 BC date and is also an exceptional find in North-Eastern Europe (Paavel 2020a; Fig. 3). The second item is a fragment of a stone axe, found already two decades ago (no 8; Johanson 2021). Also the number of Early Iron Age finds listed in

Fig. 2. A copper alloy pendant from Mõdriku (no 132).

Jn 2. Mõdriku vasesulamist ripats (nr 132).

Photo / Foto: Maria Smirnova

Fig. 3. A copper adze from Tallinn (no 43).

Jn 3. Vasest talb Tallinnast (nr 43).

(AI 8334.)

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

the table is higher than before. Two possible Pre-Roman Age iron axes stand out as rare or even unique types (nos 16, 33). A silver 5th–6th century crossbow brooch from Vinni (no 149) seems to be a unique specimen as it is the first crossbow brooch in Estonia that is decorated with a raised interlaced pattern (Tamla 2021). The lunula-shaped belt fitting or horse harness from Kulli (no 15) that can be dated to the Final Iron Age, is another unusual find (Kaseorg 2021). Analogous lunula-shaped artefacts are usually interpreted as pendants and some cases are also known from the inhumation burials, where such items were used in necklaces (see more in Kurisoo 2021). The Kulli specimen seems to have been used as a belt detail, which is indicated by the pieces of leather attached to the find and by an accompanying artefact, a rectangular belt mount, that has also survived with remains of leather. Recent years have also increased the number of ornaments that are considered to be of Finnish origin. A well-preserved equal-armed brooch from the Viking Age was found in Ärina (no 152) and a possible fragment of another in Aa (no 55). In addition, two sites have yielded iron blooms (nos 55, 62), which cannot be precisely dated, but which offer valuable insights to iron production.

Three Modern Period stray finds deserve to be pointed out, all from Harju County. The first of them, a find from Kemba (no 11) is probably a bridle boss. The find is decorated with the Royal Monogram of King Charles XII of Sweden, this object may possibly originate from the horse harness of royal cavalry and as such it fits well into the historical context when Estonia was under the Swedish rule (Russow 2021a). The second find, an Early Modern Period gun barrel from Padise (no 28) was first not recognised as an archaeological object and the finder tried to sell it online. Luckily, its historical value was noticed and the gun barrel was brought to the MA and will be stored in the archaeological collections after its cultural value has been assessed. Ülgase silver finger ring with a Calvary motif (no 54) was recognised by the finder as an archaeological object two decades after he made the discovery, after having attended a training course by the MA (Russow 2020). It is possible that the Ülgase finger ring was associated with a member of ecclesiastical order (Russow 2021b).

WESTERN PARTS OF ESTONIA (LÄÄNE, PÄRNU, AND SAARE COUNTIES)

Similarly to previous years, the number of find spots reported from the western parts of Estonia is modest (Table 1; Fig. 1). More information is available about the search activities on the island of Saaremaa, where 25 discoveries were listed, but some of the finds were actually made years ago and handed over to the MA in 2020. Four discoveries were listed from Lääne County and seven from Pärnu County. Less than one-third of the finds seem to originate from archaeological sites, mostly burial sites (nos 118, 174, 178, 181, 183, 185, 190). These are generally Viking Age and/or Final Iron Age cremation burials where pieces of ornaments and dress accessories dominate among finds.

A small 16th-century coin-hoard, which might have been the contents of a purse, was discovered in Eametsa (no 156). As the youngest coin of the assemblage was minted in 1557, it can be assumed that the Eametsa hoard dates from the very beginning of the Livonian War

(Leimus 2020). In addition, ten Russian silver wire coins, possibly from a hoard of the Early Modern Period, were collected in Kalli (no 158).

The oldest stray find from the western parts of Estonia comes from the island of Saaremaa and is dated to the Bronze Age (no 186, see photo on p. 292). The Läägi spearhead belongs to the Bagterp type of spearheads, which were common in Scandinavia and northern Germany (Paavel 2020b and ref. therein). Bronze Age spearheads are rare finds in Estonia and Läägi is the tenth specimen (Paavel 2020b). A few items that are associated with the first half of the Iron Age can be highlighted, too. These include a Roman coin (no 195), a 4th–7th century knife (no 176) and two fragments of a 5th–6th century silver neck ring (no 116). Finds that originate from the second half of the Iron Age are numerous and widespread types of ornaments and dress accessories. Among the less common items are a pair of tweezers from Vedruka (no 198), which may date to the end of the prehistory, but a somewhat later date cannot be excluded (Luik 2020). As in northern Estonia, a 7th century small equal-armed brooch with a high arch and decorated with parallel grooves points to the Finnish connections (no 195; e.g., Lehtosalo-Hilander 1982, 86–89).

The most common are Modern Period stray finds and they include items such as coins, dress accessories, and various tools. A disc-shaped object that was found from Pusku is a unique item in the Estonian archaeological record. The object is made of fire gilt gun-metal and is decorated with a grinning face that wears a hat (Fig. 4), probably depicting a specific character from antiquity or Early Modern Period culture, but more research is needed for final specification. According to Erki Russow (2021c) it is likely that the disc was part of a decorated harness and on the basis of the stylistic analysis it seems to originate from the 16th–17th centuries.

Fig. 4. A bridle boss from Pusku (no 117).

Jn 4. Pusku valjanaast (nr 117).

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

SOUTHERN PARTS OF ESTONIA (JÕGEVA, VILJANDI, PÕLVA, TARTU, VALGA, AND VÕRU COUNTIES)

A similar number of find spots is recorded from the southern parts of Estonia as in the year before (Kurisoo *et al.* 2020, 268), with some minor changes in the geographical distribution (Table 1; Fig. 1). Most of the find spots are associated with Jõgeva County, where the number of discoveries has never been so high. Less than 20 finding places are recorded from Tartu County. Following a previously established pattern, only a small number of sites are listed from Viljandi (3), Põlva (3), Valga (6) and Võru (4) Counties.

Around 50 percent of finding places indicate some type of archaeological site, of which settlement sites are most numerous (e.g. nos 77, 78, 80, 93, 94, 97, 199, 202, 208, 210, 216, 221) followed by a diversity of burial sites (e.g. nos 77, 82, 85, 86, 205, 214, 225, 226). The latter include mostly Viking Age and/or Final Iron Age cremations (e.g. nos 85, 86, 214). Two medieval and post-medieval village cemeteries with inhumation burials are listed in the Table (nos 205, 226). Additionally, four hoards were unearthed of which one is a possible Viking Age coin hoard (no 209) and the others belong to the Early Modern Period (nos 217, 218, 221).

The latter were found in Valga County and each contained different pieces of Early Modern Period jewellery such as sheet pendants and large silver beads. The exact content of the Lota hoard (no 218) is not entirely clear and it seems to have been mixed with contemporaneous stray finds from the area. It is likely that the fragments of a neck ornament made of coins were part of the deposit, as analogous cases from the present-day Valga County suggest (e.g. Kiudsoo 2008, 117; Tvauri 2014; Rammo *et al.* 2014, fig. 6; Rammo 2020b). These hoards have been dated to the 16th and the beginning of the 17th century and it seems likely that they were abandoned because of the famine in the years 1601–1603 or the Swedish-Polish wars in South Estonia in the beginning of the 17th century (Tvauri 2014).

The majority of the dwelling sites can be dated from the Middle Ages to the Modern Period (e.g. nos 87, 88, 90, 94, 199, 202, 208, 220). Collected artefacts range from diverse metal items (e.g., buttons, rings, brooches, book clasps) to pottery (e.g., wheel-thrown pottery). The earliest settlement site listed in the Table is Lammiku (no 203), where besides metal items, flint and quartz flakes from the Mesolithic were collected. Quartz flakes in Reastvere find assemblage (no 93) indicate a Stone Age dwelling site as well. Furthermore, there seems to be a wider positive trend: more hobby searchers recognise diverse archaeological objects made of different materials (e.g., flint and bone/antler) that they encounter during their searches. For instance, the entire dataset contains more sherds of pottery than before (e.g. nos 202, 213) and several iron blooms (see above). A medieval bone comb from Meerapalu (no 154) is another example of that practice.

The earliest stray finds from the southern parts of Estonia are two Roman Iron Age items – a finger-ring (no 96) and a cross-ribbed brooch (no 227). Late Iron Age finds are more numerous and some of them belong to the rare types of objects. For example, Piilsi fire-steel pendant (no 91) that depicts two horsemen deserves to be pointed out. Only a few such finds are known from Estonia and they can be dated to approximately the Viking Age (Juurik 2021a). The rider motif is believed to be of eastern origin, but the majority of analogues objects are known from Finland and the pendant can be regarded as another example of a Finnish type artefact (Lehtosalo-Hilander 1982, 72–75; Salo 1990, 56–57).

As in previous years, a large number of artefacts have been collected from the shallow water near the shore of Lake Peipsi (nos 155, 206, 207, 208, 211, 213, 228, 229). Early Modern and Modern Period personal items – such as cruciform pendants, ear-spoons, finger-rings – originate from sunken dwelling sites and burials. These finds express the peculiarities in the culture of the historical Russian settlement on the lake's shore. Early Modern and Modern Period mass material is overwhelming among the collected items, but it is difficult to exploit their potential in research as the function of these items often remains unidentified. For example, the mounts with zoomorphic decoration, known from several sites in eastern and southern Estonia, adorned a type of Late Medieval leather purses related with Novgorod (Juurik 2021b and ref. therein; Osipenko 2016; Fig. 5), which tells us more about past contacts and consumption habits. Also, an Early Modern Period assemblage of iron items unearthed in Selgise (no 213) is significant. A set of specific details, such as a lock and a lock cover, suggest that Selgise items were stored in a wooden chest. The chest may have functioned as a storage unit for scrap metal that included several unidentifiable iron objects in addition to an axe and a spur (Saage 2021).

Fig. 5. Zoomorphic mounts from Kuusiku (on the left; no 202) and one from Lake Peipsi near Päärissaare (on the right; no 207). The key, which can also be associated with these purses, was found from Lake Peipsi in 2021. The drawing is based on a well-preserved find from Novgorod (Osipenko 2016, fig. 1).

Jn 5. Kuusiku külast (vasakul; nr 202) ja Päärissaare lähistelt Peipsi järvest (paremal; nr 207) leitud loomakujutisega kotinaastud. Sama tüüpi nahkotikeste juurde kuulub ka võti, mis leiti 2021. a Peipsi järvest. Joonise aluseks on Novgorodi hästi säilinud leid (Osipenko 2016, jn 1).

Photos and drawing / Fotod ja joonis: Riina Rammo

DISCUSSION: THE USE OF SEARCHING DEVICES AND ISSUES RELATED TO THE PRACTICE

Table 1 includes hundreds of finds and more than 200 sites, but these impressive numbers do not reflect the efficiency of the current system. Quite the opposite, the amount of finds that are collected and handed over to heritage specialists has completely overburdened the MA. The specificity of the Estonian system includes archaeologists, who assist heritage specialists by writing expert opinions on collected finds and respective find spots, which are the basis for further steps for the MA (e.g., additional fieldwork). Another bottleneck that influences the efficiency is the small number of archaeologists who assess the cultural value of collected artefacts and compile the reports. For example, less than a quarter of the finds listed in Table 1 were examined by experts within the time limit set by the law.

All this causes long delays in providing feedback to hobby searchers and hinders the process of acknowledgements and rewards. Both aspects have a negative impact on cooperation between the hobby searches and the MA. Additionally, this situation seems to be one of the reasons why several permit holders continue unearthing finds from the known find spots. These finding places are not under state protection as archaeological monuments or as protected archaeological sites, thus no restrictions apply for search activities. In some cases, hobby searchers have caused significant harm to the sites by digging up too many finds and failing to provide adequate documentation. There are also cases when a new person rediscovers the same find spot and unearths more finds from that particular place. For instance, Kõmmaste burial site (no 17) has been reported several times by different persons (Rammo *et al.* 2014, table 1: 2; Rammo & Kangert 2018, table 1: 10), but the same can be said about several other find spots (see also Kurisoo *et al.* 2020, 264; Rammo & Kangert 2018, 210; Rammo & Smirnova 2019, 269).

On the other hand, there are cases when the MA advises additional searches in a certain area, sometimes near known monuments, which helps to locate the borders of these sites with better accuracy. However, this kind of cooperation only works when the hobby

searchers are well informed, ready to meticulously document their findings and do not unearth an unnecessary amount of items. Therefore, the best protection of the archaeological sites seems to be awareness of the importance of cultural heritage and a sincere wish to cooperate. Further steps need to be taken to overcome the current obstacles caused by the large influx of metal-detector finds and slow processing of these finds and find spots.

One solution is to change the format of expert opinions that would also allow shorter reports beside comprehensive overviews. Also, more archaeology students could be included in the process of assessing the cultural value of the collected finds, which benefits both sides. Students will gain more experience on determining artefacts and analysing the cultural landscape, and at the same time, more hobby searchers will receive feedback on time. There are also more archaeologists working at the MA than ever before, allowing us to be more optimistic about the future: more find spots can be inspected by the local heritage specialists and when necessary, taken under state protection.

SUMMARISING REMARKS

Similarly to the previous years, the search activities were concentrated in the northern parts of Estonia, especially in and around Harju County. More information was gained about Lääne-Viru and Jõgeva County than during earlier years, but many of the discoveries reported in 2020 were actually made years ago. Additionally, it seemed that more people were willing to report their unlicensed search activities. Although in many cases the information about these find spots is incomplete, the situation indicates that the importance of cultural heritage is more broadly acknowledged in the society. This is also testified by the variability of collected finds, which include objects made of diverse materials from all time periods. The oldest finds mentioned in this paper are from the Stone Age, followed by a few Bronze Age items. There are more objects from the Iron Age, but the majority of the artefacts associate with the period from the end of the prehistory to the end of the modern era.

The number of hobbyists is growing yearly, which also means more workload for heritage specialists and archaeologists, who are involved in the process of assessing the cultural value of the metal-detector finds. The large number of artefacts and finding places that need to be evaluated has a direct impact on the efficiency of the system, causing delays in feedback and examining these sites on the spot. It is hoped that by changing the current format of expert opinions the processing of finds and find spots picks up speed and helps to solve one of the current bottlenecks.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to all who contributed to compiling the table and provided the illustrations, especially to Kristiina Johanson, Riina Juurik, Aivar Kriiska, Heidi Luik, Ain Mäesalu, Michael Neiß, Mari-Liis Posti, Jaana Ratas, Ragnar Saage, Andres Tvauri and Andres Vindi. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 101003387 and Noor-Eesti research grant of Postimees Foundation (POST4).

Table 1. Finds discovered by users of searching devices and stray finds reported to the National Heritage Board in 2020. Former parish name (if different from the present municipality name) is given in brackets.

Tabel 1. Otsinguvahendiga leitud ja juhuslikult avastatud leiud, mis jõudsid 2020. a Muinsuskaitseametisse. Sulgudes on esitatud kihelkond, juhul kui see erineb kehtivast haldusjaotusest.

Compiled by / Koostanud: Maria Smirnova, Riina Rammo, Tuuli Kurisoo

C – cemetery, burial place / kalmistu, matmispaik

F – stray find / juhuleid

H – hoard, deposit find / peitleid

S – settlement site / asulakoht

SP – sacrificial place / ohverdamiskoht

HS – harbour site / sadamakoht

No / Site / Nr Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiur nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert	
HARJUMAA								
1	Aila	F	Saue (Keila)	Head of dress pin	Final Iron Age	AI 8529	V. Blinov	R. Rammo
2	Alliku	F	Saue (Keila)	Fragment of zoomorphic pendant and penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		D. Iskanders	M. Kaseorg
3	Hatu	C?, S	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Coins, coin pendant, cruciform pendant, fragments of copper alloy ornaments (e.g. dress pin, pendant, bracelet), belt fittings, mounts, iron finger-ring, knives, rivets, rings, lead seal	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8316	H. Järvis	H. Luik
4	Hatu	F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Cruciform pendant fragment, pewter bead, melted items, knife fragment, iron ring, needle	Middle Ages – Modern Period		H. Järvis	
5	Humala	C, S	Harku (Keila)	Coin, dress pin, penannular brooch, lunula pendant, trapezoid pendant, metal bead, bell, belt fittings, mounts, sword fragment, book clasps, waist ornament fragment, stone spindle whorl, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period	AI 8432, AI 8433	A. Sudovykh, Anonymous	M. Reppo
6	Igavere	F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Buckle, waist ornament, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8326	T. Vaik, J. Ojabstein	M.-L. Posti
7	Jägala	H?	Jõelähtme	Pewter beads, finger-ring	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period	AI 8323	A. Ende	M.-L. Posti
8	Järsi	F	Raasiku (Jüri)	Stone axe fragment	Neolithic		Anonymous	K. Johanson
9	Kalesi	C?	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Fragments of copper alloy ornaments (pendants, bracelet, mount, strap end)	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		D. Iskanders	M. Kaseorg
10	Kautjala	C?	Rae (Jüri)	Bracelet	Roman Iron Age	AI 8436	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
11	Kemba	F	Kuusalu	Bridle boss	Early Modern Period	AI 8458	S. Kolesnikov	E. Russow
12	Kiia	C, F	Saue (Keila)	Cruciform pendants, silver zoomorphic brooch fragment, bracelets, rectangular ornament link, buckle, decorated mount	Migration Period – Pre-Viking Age, Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		M. Kobets	

No / Site / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
13	Kirivalla	F	Kose	Cruciform pendant, signet finger-ring, metal bead fragment	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period	AI 8320	A. Kivistik	M.-L. Posti
14	Kuivajõe	F	Kose	Scale weight, metal bead fragment, round brooch fragment, belt fittings, wheel-thrown pottery	Viking Age – Modern Period	AI 8321	A. Kivistik	M.-L. Posti
15	Kulli	F	Raasiku (Jüri)	Belt fittings (mounts, lunula-shaped pendant, leather)	Final Iron Age		D. Iskanders	M. Kaseorg
16	Kurna	F	Rae (Jüri)	Iron axe	Pre-Roman Iron Age(?)		M. Kobets	
17	Kõmmaste	C, F	Lääne-Nigula (Risti)	Burnt jewellery fragments (brooches, chains, pendants, bracelet, spiral tubes), belt fittings, fire-steel, pommel, mounts, bells, iron socketed axe, metal items, glazed pottery sherd	Pre-Roman Iron Age, Viking Age, Modern Period		H. Järvis	
18	Lehetu	F	Saue (Nissi)	Coin pendant, penannular brooch, belt fittings, button	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
19	Lehmja	F	Rae (Jüri)	Axe	Early Modern Period		V. Volkov	
20	Lehmja	F	Rae (Jüri)	Pewter pendant	Modern Period		V. Volkov	
21	Liikva	H	Harku (Keila)	Silver coins	Viking Age	AI 8462	H. Järvis	I. Leimus
22	Maardu	SP?	Jõelähtme	Neck-rings, dress pins, chain holder, chain separators, plaque, bracelet, metal beads, pendant fragment, chain links, spiral tubes	Migration Period – Viking Age	AI 8426	Anonymous	R. Rammo
23	Muraste	F	Harku (Keila)	Roman coin	Roman Iron Age		H. Järvis	
24	Nurme	C, F	Saue (Nissi)	Silver coin, small round brooch, partly burnt jewellery (e.g. ornament links, penannular brooches, dress pins, chain arrangement details, bracelets) and belt fittings, bridle boss, scale weights	Viking Age, Final Iron Age, Modern Period		Anonymous	
25	Nurme	F	Saue (Nissi)	Pendants	Final Iron Age(?)		Anonymous	
26	Nurme	S	Saue (Nissi)	Silver coin, finger-ring, buckle	Viking Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	
27	Ohtu	C, S?	Lääne-Harju (Keila)	Copper alloy jewellery fragments (cruciform pendant, penannular brooch, round brooches, bracelet), trapezoid pendant, finger-ring, belt fittings, sword scabbard chape, ornament links, metal items	Viking Age – Early Modern Period	AI 8431	A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo
28	Padise	F	Lääne-Harju (Harju-Madise)	Gun barrel	Early Modern Period		Anonymous	
29	Pae	F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Crossbow bolt	Middle Ages	AI 8313	H. Järvis	H. Luik

No / Site / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
30	Pae	C, F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Lunula-shaped pendant, jewellery fragments (e.g. dress pin head), belt fittings, scale weight, rings, fragments of metal items, lead seal	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Järvis	
31	Parila	C?, S	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Dress pin fragment, rectangular ornament link, coins, coin pendant, buttons, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8498	Anonymous	M. Reppo
32	Peningi	F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Fragments of copper alloy ornaments (penannular brooch, cruciform pendant, waist ornament)	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		D. Iskanders	M. Kaseorg
33	Pikavere	F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Iron axe	Pre-Roman Iron Age – Roman Iron Age		Anonymous	
34	Raveliku	C, S	Kose	Coins, coin pendants, disc brooch, animal figurine, various brooches, pendants, finger-rings, ornament links, chain separator, beads, bells, burnt jewellery fragments, scabbard chapes, belt fittings, scale weights, iron axe, knife, fragments of metal vessel, bullet, flint flake	Roman Iron Age, Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8506, AI 8507, AI 8508, AI 8509	A. Agurajuja	M. Tammet, I. Leimus, M. Reppo
35	Ruu	S	Jõelähtme	Trapezoid pendant, finger-ring, bells	Middle Ages – Modern Period	AI 8455, AI 8532	Anonymous, V. Tkatchuk	M. Reppo
36	Saha	F	Jõelähtme	Bird-shaped pendant	Final Iron Age		R. Sementsenko	
37	Salu	S, F	Rae (Harju-Jaani)	Trapezoid pendant, bells, finger-ring, jewellery fragments (penannular brooch, chain, bracelets), buckle fragment	Viking Age, Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		D. Iskanders	M. Kaseorg
38	Saula	S	Kose	Finger-ring, pendant, waist ornament detail, buckle, ornament fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8312	A. Poznanski	H. Luik
39	Saunja	S	Kuusalu (Jõelähtme)	Coin pendants, pewter pendant	Early Modern Period – Modern Period	AI 8329	Anonymous	M.-L. Posti
40	Saunja	F	Kuusalu (Jõelähtme)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	M. Kaseorg
41	Soodevahe	F	Rae (Jüri)	Chain holder, spearhead	Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8314, AI 8330	J. Tkatchenko	H. Luik
42	Suurküla	F	Lääne-Harju (Harju-Madise)	Penannular brooch, chain separator, mount, bell, buttons	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		R. Randlane	
43	Tallinn	F	Tallinn city (Tallinn)	Copper adze	Neolithic	AI 8334	J. Tkatchenko	K. Paavel
44	Tammiku	F	Kose	Finger-rings, knife handle detail, metal pot handle, mount, slag, pottery sherd	Modern Period	AI 8319	A. Kivistik	M.-L. Posti
45	Tuula	F	Saue (Keila)	Cloth seal	Early Modern Period	AI 8457	K. Hiimäe	E. Russow

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46	Vaidasoo	F	Rae (Jüri)	Coins, jewellery fragments (penannular brooch, bracelet, coin pendants, pendant, chain, mount), knife handle fragment, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		T. Nikklus	
47	Valgejõe	F	Kuusalu (Haljala)	Javelin head, spur	Final Iron Age, Middle Ages	AI 8450	Anonymous	A. Tvauri
48	Valgejõe	F	Kuusalu (Haljala)	Plano-convex slag cake	Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8451	Anonymous	A. Tvauri
49	Valingu	H	Saue (Keila)	Chain arrangement (chains, chain holders, separators, bells), pendants, knife sheath elements, waist ornaments (spiral tubes, links), pewter mounts, penannular brooch, spiral tubes	Final Iron Age	AI 8342	V. Blinov	R. Rammo
50	Valkla	C?	Jõelähtme (Kuusalu)	Animal figurine, bird-shaped pendant, finger-ring, mount	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8490	Anonymous	M. Reppo
51	Vaskjala	F	Rae (Jüri)	Mace head, penannular brooches, round brooch, bell, buckle, tobacco pipe cleaner, needle case, button, lead seals	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Tkatchenko	R. Saage, T. Borgia
52	Veneküla	F	Rae (Jüri)	Round copper alloy pendant	Middle Ages – Modern Period		A. Lysenko	
53	Vilama	F	Kose	Dress pins, strap end, mount	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	S. Jegorov
54	Ülgase	F	Jõelähtme	Silver ring	Middle Ages	AI 8402	D. Meleševits	E. Russow
IDA-VIRUMAA								
55	Aa	C, S, F	Lüganuse	Socketed axe, cross-bow brooches, round convex brooch, equal-armed brooch fragment, penannular brooch, bird-shaped pendant, dress pin fragment, bracelet, ornament fragments, rings, sword scabbard chape, book clasp, lock cover, iron blooms, knives, metal items	Roman Iron Age, Migration Period – Modern Period		E. Kessel, A. Smirnov, A. Kotkin	R. Saage
56	Atsalama	C	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Pendant, bell, finger-rings, jewellery fragments (brooch pin, bracelets, chains), rings, needle, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8456	Anonymous	M. Tammet
57	Erra-Liiva	C, F	Lüganuse	Bracelet, burnt jewellery (e.g. enamelled brooch, bracelets, rectangular ornament link, spiral tube), mount, sword fragment	Roman Iron Age, Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		T. Leinbok	M. Kaseorg

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58	Kohtla-Järve	F	Kohtla-Järve town (Jõhvi)	Eye brooch fragment	Roman Iron Age		V. Rummyantsev	
59	Kuru	F	Alutaguse (Iisaku)	Cruciform pendant, bracelets, penannular brooch fragment	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8495	G. Niinepuu	K. Karro
60	Matka	C, F	Lüganuse	Burnt jewellery fragments (crossbow brooches, cross-ribbed brooch, bracelets, disc brooch, finger-rings, bead), buckles, scale weight, knife, nails, metal items	Roman Iron Age, Viking Age – Final Iron Age, Modern Period		T. Leinbok	
61	Metsa-mägara	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Fragment of knife or sickle	Middle or Late Bronze Age	AI 8513	Anonymous	K. Paavel
62	Metsa-mägara	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Penannular brooch fragment, slag, melted glass, iron blooms(?), metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
63	Metsa-mägara	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Cloth seal	Early Modern Period	AI 8474	Anonymous	E. Russow
64	Mõisamaa	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Cruciform pendant fragment, silver coin, finger-ring, silver sheet fragments, buckle, cross-bow bolt(?), iron items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Kessel	
65	Pagari	F	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Axe	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		V. Rummyantsev	
66	Peeri	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Cruciform pendant fragment, buckle, knives, metal objects, slag	Final Iron Age(?) – Modern Period		E. Kessel	
67	Roodu	F	Toila (Lüganuse)	Scale weights, metal items	Viking Age – Final Iron Age, Modern Period		E. Kessel	
68	Saka	F	Toila (Lüganuse)	Ornament fragments (e.g. dress pin), iron item	Final Iron Age(?)		E. Kessel	
69	Saka	F	Toila (Lüganuse)	Penannular brooch fragment	Viking Age		R. Vinkler	
70	Soldina	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Coins, penannular brooch fragment, mount	Viking Age – Modern Period		D. Šutov	H. Luik
71	Vainu	F	Lüganuse	Spearhead fragment, axe, spur	Viking Age – Modern Period		T. Leinbok	
72	Varesmetsa	F	Alutaguse (Iisaku)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		H. Välimets	M. Kaseorg
73	Vasavere	F	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Crossbow bolt, iron item, slag	Middle Ages		E. Kessel	
74	Varja	F	Lüganuse	Iron socketed axe	Roman Iron Age		E. Kessel	
75	Varja	C, S	Lüganuse	Coin, burnt jewellery fragments (bracelets, penannular brooch, pendant), finger-ring, belt fittings, knife, metal items	Viking Age - Modern Period	AI 8463, AI 8464, AI 8465, AI 8466, AI 8535	Anonymous, E. Kessel	M. Tammet
76	Vodava	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Penannular brooch	Viking Age		A. Smirnov	S. Jegorov

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JÕGEVAMAA								
77	Alavere	C?, S	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Coins, crossbow bolt, jewellery fragments (bracelet, heart-shaped brooch), bell, thimble, burnt copper alloy items	Viking Age – Modern Period		E. Pärtelpoeg	H. Luik
78	Alavere	S, SP?, F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Coin, penannular brooch, pendants (e.g. trapezoid), chain holder, bracelets, round brooch, finger-ring, mounts, book clasp, jewellery fragments	Viking Age – Modern Period		K. Keske, A. Ostrat	
79	Avinurme	F	Mustvee (Torma)	Javelin head	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	R. Juurik
80	Härjanurme	S	Jõgeva (Kursi)	Fragments of copper alloy pot	Modern Period		K. Keske	
81	Imukvere	F	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Narrow-bladed axe with narrow polls	Pre-Viking Age – Viking Age		Anonymous	
82	Kaavere	C?, F	Põltsamaa (Kolga-Jaani)	Penannular brooches, cruciform pendant, round pendant, finger-rings, ornament link, scale weight, spiral tubes, bell	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages, Modern Period		V. Bortnik	
83	Kaarepere	F	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Finger-rings, belt fitting	Middle Ages – Modern Period		V. Bortnik	
84	Kaliküla	F	Põltsamaa	Dress pin heads, bird-shaped pendant, bracelet	Final Iron Age		V. Bortnik	
85	Laiusevälja	C, F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Burnt copper alloy fragments (e.g. brooches, bracelets, comb-shaped pendant, ornament links, belt fittings, spiral tubes), scale weight, buttons, bullets, thimble, metal items	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		E. Pärtelpoeg, A. Samarin	S. Jegorov
86	Lebavere	C	Põltsamaa (Pilistvere)	Burnt jewellery fragments	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		U. Kuusik	S. Sammler
87	Loopre	S?	Põltsamaa	Coins, small round brooch, signet finger-ring, penannular brooch pin, bell, rings, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		O. Rubel	S. Jegorov
88	Mõhküla	S?	Põltsamaa	Bracelet fragment, trapezoid pendant, fire-steel, knife, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		U. Kuusik	
89	Oti	F	Jõgeva (Torma)	Javelin head	Final Iron Age		R. Alberi	R. Juurik
90	Palupere	S?	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Coins, cruciform pendant, mounts, ear-spoon, signet finger-rings, buttons, dice, lead seal, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		E. Pärtelpoeg	
91	Piilsi	F	Mustvee (Torma)	Fire-steel pendant	Viking Age(?)		R. Alberi	R. Juurik
92	Raaduvere	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	S-shaped pendant	Final Iron Age		A. Sudovykh	M. Reppo

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93	Reastvere	C?, S, F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Coins, coin pendants, penannular brooches, finger-rings, pendants, bracelets, rectangular ornament link, belt fittings, needle case, button, earring, bridle details, burnt metal items, metal items, tripod fragments, pottery sherds, quartz flakes	Stone Age, Viking Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	M. Niine-salu
94	Selli	S, F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Coins, coin pendants, cruciform pendant, chain fragment, mounts, finger-rings, bells, spiral tube, thimble, metal items	Viking Age, Middle Ages – Modern Period		P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	
95	Tapiku	F	Põltsamaa	Cruciform pendants, star-shaped brooch	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		V. Bortnik	
96	Tooma	F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Chain holder, finger-ring	Roman Iron Age, Final Iron Age		V. Rumyantsev	
97	Änkküla	S	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Dress pin head, cruciform pendant, bracelet fragment, rectangular ornament link, book clasp, buckle, metal items	Final Iron Age, Middle Ages		K. Keske, J. Naaber	S. Jegorov
JÄRVAMAA								
98	Allikjärve	SP?	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Scythes or sickles	Viking Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	
99	Jalgsema	F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Palstave	Early Bronze Age		M. Põvvat	K. Paavel
100	Jõgisoo	S	Järva (Ambla)	Bracelet, bell, jewellery fragments (e.g. penannular brooch, round sheet pendant), fragment, hand-made pottery	Viking Age – Middle Ages		A. Kivistik	H. Luik
101	Kaaruka	F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Coins, coin pendants, cruciform pendant, trapezoid pendant, bracelet fragment, bells, scale weight, belt fittings, rings, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Vares	
102	Kaaruka	F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Crossbow brooch fragment	Roman Iron Age		E. Promm	
103	Kagavere	C?, F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Coin pendants, jewellery fragments, penannular brooch, belt fittings, rectangular ornament links, finger-ring, scale weight, sword fragments, spearhead, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period	AI 8524	H. Vaalundi	
104	Kalitsa	F	Järva (Koeru)	Round pendant, coin pendants, coin, finger-ring, bells, mounts, jewellery fragments, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		O. Rubel	
105	Laimetsa	F	Järva (Pilstvere)	Signet finger-ring, spiral finger-ring, buckle, ornament fragments, quartz flake	Early Modern Period	AI 8421	R. Pahapill	M.-L. Posti

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106	Lõõla	F	Türi	Penannular brooch, dress pin fragments, book clasps, metal items	Final Iron Age, Early Modern Period, Modern Period		J. Leesmaa	
107	Metstaguse	F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Copper alloy tool – wedge(?)	Middle Ages – Modern Period(?)		M. Põvvat	
108	Peetri	F	Järva (Peetri)	Coins, coin pendants, equal-armed brooch, jewelry fragments (penannular brooch, bracelet, rectangular ornament links, pendants, finger-ring), bells, belt fittings, buttons, silver spoon, knives, metal items, tobacco pipe fragments, wheel-thrown pottery	Roman Iron Age, Viking Age – Modern Period		R. Lallu, A. Piirsalu, M. Tammehoid	
109	Puiatu	F	Järva (Pilistvere)	Signet finger-rings, finger-ring	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		S. Bujanov	
110	Valasti	C?, S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Penannular brooch pins, tweezers, rectangular ornament link, bell, penannular brooch fragment, buckle	Viking Age – Modern Period		E. Promm, A. Vares	
111	Valasti	S, F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Coins, coin pendants, ornament fragments (pendants, bracelets, penannular brooches), rectangular ornament link, finger-rings, bells, belt fittings, ring, mounts, buttons, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Vares, E. Promm	
112	Valasti	S, F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Bow brooch, bell, small round brooch, coin pendant, knife handle detail, mounts, belt fittings, bridle details, coins, buttons, bullets, metal items	Roman Iron Age, Modern Period		A. Vares	
113	Vedruka	F	Paide town (Peetri)	Coin pendant, trapezoid pendants, metal items	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		E. Promm	
114	Vissuvere	F	Türi	Star-shaped brooch, cruciform pendant fragment, scabbard chape, strap end, mount	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		M. Kobets	

LÄÄNEMAA

115	Keskküla	F	Lääne-Nigula (Kirbla)	Coin, coin pendant, penannular brooch fragment, cruciform pendant, ring, metal item	Early Modern Period		A. Ankru	
116	Liivi	F	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Silver neck-ring fragments, finger-ring, knife, metal item	Migration Period, Middle Ages – Modern Period		J. Ojabstein	Ü. Tamla
117	Pusku	F	Haapsalu town (Ridala)	Detail of horse harness(?)	Early Modern Period		Anonymous	E. Russow

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118	Saanika	C, F	Haapsalu town (Ridala)	Coins, jewellery fragments (e.g. dress pins, pendant, penannular brooches, bracelets), bells, metal beads, belt fittings, rectangular ornament link, book clasps, knives, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Davõdov	I. Leimus
LÄÄNE-VIRUMAA								
119	Aresi	C, F	Rakvere	Bracelets, knife sheath, scale weight, pendant, axe, burnt metal items, finger-rings, ornament fragments, belt fittings, coin pendant, coins	Viking Age – Modern Period		D. Šutov	
120	Avanduse	C, F	Väike-Maarja (Simuna)	Burnt metal items, scale weight, finger-ring with glass setting	Viking Age – Final Iron Age, Early Modern Period		L. Roots	
121	Eipri	F	Väike-Maarja	Dress pin fragment, penannular brooches, star-shaped brooch, finger-rings, cruciform pendants, tobacco pipe cleaner	Viking Age – Modern Period		L. Roots	
122	Iila	C, F	Viru-Nigula	Pendants, bracelet fragment, copper alloy ornaments, strap end, button	Roman Iron Age, Migration Period – Modern Period	AI 8446, AI 8447	A. Timm	M. Tammet
123	Iila	C	Viru-Nigula	Eye brooch	Roman Iron Age	AI 8448	A. Timm	M. Tammet
124	Iila	S	Viru-Nigula	Silver neck-ring fragment, round silver pendant, pewter brooch, lock detail	Middle Ages – Modern Period	AI 8439, AI 8444	A. Timm	M. Tammet
125	Järvajõe	F	Tapa (Väike-Maarja)	Dress pin fragments	Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
126	Kamariku	F	Väike-Maarja	Cruciform pendant, finger-rings, rectangular ornament link	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		L. Roots	
127	Koila	F	Viru-Nigula	Socketed axe	Middle Bronze Age – Late Bronze Age	AI 8476	O. Kirillova	K. Paavel
128	Koila	C, F	Viru-Nigula	Chain holder, jewellery fragments (pendant, chains, bracelet, partly burnt), belt fittings, waist ornament fragments, coin, bridle mounts, ring, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		O. Kirillova, K. Koppe	
129	Levala	F	Rakvere	Dress pin fragments, scale weight, finger-ring	Roman Iron Age, Viking Age – Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
130	Levala	C, F	Rakvere	Penannular brooch, horse-shaped pendant, finger-rings, jewellery fragments (brooch pin, melted objects), bridle mount, buttons	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		L. Roots	

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131	Liivaküla	F	Väike-Maarja	Book clasps, belt fittings	Early Modern Period, Modern Period		L. Roots	
132	Mõdriku	C, S, F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Pendants, penannular brooch, dress pin head, equal-armed brooch, finger-rings, belt fittings, rectangular ornament link, bells, jewellery fragments (bracelet, penannular brooch), burnt jewellery, metal beads, book clasps, button, bridle details, spoon fragment, axe, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		T. Vaide	
133	Nurkse	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Belt mounts, buckle, ornament fragment, bell	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages(?)		Anonymous	
134	Nõmme	F	Väike-Maarja	Lunula pendant, cruciform pendant, finger-ring	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		L. Roots	
135	Ohepalu	C, F	Kadrina	Jewellery fragments (dress pin head, cruciform pendant, waist ornament), belt fittings, ingot, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
136	Palasi	H	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Coins	Early Modern Period	AI 8338	E. Kessel	M. Kiudsoo, I. Leimus
137	Piibe	F	Väike-Maarja (Koeru)	Coin pendant, knife	Early Modern Period		P. Laidre	R. Saage
138	Piibe	F	Väike-Maarja (Koeru)	Knife, arrow-head, rings, scythe fragment, metal item	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period(?)		P. Laidre	R. Saage
139	Piibe	F	Väike-Maarja (Koeru)	Arrow-head, knives	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period(?)		P. Laidre	R. Saage
140	Pruuna	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Annular brooch (inscription AVE MARIA)	Middle Ages		Anonymous	
141	Raeküla	C	Väike-Maarja	Burnt metal items (e.g. bracelets, chain holder, penannular brooches, chain)	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
142	Räsna	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Coin, signet finger-ring, ornament fragments (e.g. bracelet), mount, pewter mounts, bell, metal items	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		E. Promm, D. Doroškevitš	
143	Sirevere	F	Vinni (Simuna)	Coins, scale weight, pewter pendant, belt fitting, bridle mount	Viking Age – Modern Period		L. Roots	
144	Vao	F	Väike-Maarja	Bracelet, jewellery fragments (e.g. dress pins, fragments of penannular brooches, chain, pendants), animal-shaped pendant, cruciform pendant, round pendant, finger-rings, bell, book clasp, knife handle detail	Viking Age – Modern Period		L. Roots	
145	Vao	F	Väike-Maarja	Rectangular ornament link, bell, metal bead, penannular brooch pin, chain fragment, belt fittings, bullets, metal items	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		L. Roots	

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146	Vana-Vinni	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Dress pin	Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
147	Vasta	F	Viru-Nigula	Cruciform pendants	Middle Ages	AI 8327	D. Šutov	M.-L. Posti
148	Vetiku	F	Vinni (Rakvere)	Enamelled cruciform pendant, pewter cruciform pendant, finger-ring, bell, mount	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period		L. Roots	
149	Vinni	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Silver crossbow brooch	Migration Period	AI 8480	H. Kuus	Ü. Tamla
150	Äntu	F	Väike-Maarja	Pendant, fragment of penannular brooch, bell	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		L. Roots	
151	Äntu	F	Väike-Maarja	Silver coin pendant, strap end	Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
152	Ärina	F	Väike-Maarja	Equal-armed brooch, trapezoid pendant, bells, jewellery fragments (dress pin, penannular brooches), button, belt fitting, metal items	Viking Age – Final Iron Age, Modern Period		L. Roots	
PÖLVAMAA								
153	Karste	F	Kanepi	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages	TÜ 2924	Anonymous	S. Aarla
154	Meerapalu	F	Räpina	Bone comb	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	
155	Pedaspää, Meerapalu	F	Võnnu, Räpina	Coins, coin pendants, cruciform pendants, heart-shaped brooch, penannular brooch fragment, finger-rings, belt fittings, buttons, axe, knives, crampon, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
PÄRNUMAA								
156	Eametsa	H	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Coins	Late Middle Ages		Anonymous	I. Leimus
157	Ertsma	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Coins, penannular brooch, finger-ring, button, metal item	Early Modern Period – Modern Period		Anonymous	M. Kaseorg
158	Kalli	H?	Lääneranna (Mihkli)	Coins	Early Modern Period		K. Kipper	
159	Metsavere	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Round pendant fragment, spiral finger-ring, bell	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		Anonymous	
160	Samliku	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Vändra)	Cruciform pendant	Final Iron Age		P. Maanus	H. Luik
161	Viluvere	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Vändra)	Silver coin fragment, coin pendant, pendant, strap end	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period		Anonymous	
162	Väljaküla	F	Saarde	Round brooch, finger-rings	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	

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RAPLAMAA								
163	Adila	F	Kohila (Hageri)	Seal matrix, penannular brooch, signet finger-ring	Final Iron Age, Early Modern Period – Modern Period	AI 8403, AI 8453	I. Krause	M. Tammet, E. Russow
164	Alaküla	C?, F	Märjamaa	Coin pendant, finger-rings, belt fittings, burnt copper alloy items	Viking Age – Modern Period	AI 8505	J. Klimov	M. Reppo
165	Kohatu	C, S	Märjamaa	Penannular brooch fragment, coin pendant, fragments of copper alloy items	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period	AI 8467, AI 8470	Anonymous	M. Tammet
166	Laukna	F	Märjamaa (Kullamaa)	Coins, bracelets, spiral finger-ring, trapezoid pendant, bell, bead, rectangular ornament link, belt fittings, metal items	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period		A. Ankrü	
167	Lümandu	C, F	Märjamaa	Coins, jewellery fragments (e.g. dress pins, bracelet, pendant, finger-ring, penannular brooch), mounts, buckle, metal item	Viking Age – Final Iron Age, Early Modern Period		T. Hiob, A. Skröpnik	
168	Purga	C, F	Märjamaa	Coin, bracelet fragment, burnt metal items, ornament fragment, nail, metal items	Viking Age – Middle Ages	AI 8499	A. Skröpnik	H. Luik
169	Ringuta	F	Märjamaa	Mace head	Final Iron Age		M. Toomepuu	R. Saage
170	Sipa	C?	Märjamaa (Kullamaa)	Spur	Viking Age	AI 8309	A. Skröpnik	Ü. Tamla
171	Sipa	C	Märjamaa (Kullamaa)	Coin, burnt copper alloy items (mount, dress pin fragment)	Viking Age – Final Iron Age	AI 8468, AI 8469	Anonymous	M. Tammet
172	Sötke	F	Märjamaa	Copper alloy bar(?)	Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
173	Tolli	C	Märjamaa	Pommel, burnt copper alloy items (penannular brooches, dress pin, chain, finger-ring, belt fittings, scale weights), ring, bone fragments	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		J. Klimov	M. Reppo
SAAREMAA								
174	Are	C	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Animal-shaped figurine, scale weights, penannular brooch, shepherd's crook pin, rectangular ornament link, burnt jewellery fragments (e.g. dress pins, mounts, bracelet)	Iron Age		A. Palkov	A. Kütt
175	Asuküla	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Rectangular ornament link, trapezoid pendant, brooch fragment, buckle, anthropomorphic mount	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period		K. Laane	
176	Hübja	F	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Knife	Roman Iron Age – Pre-Viking Age		Anonymous	M. Tammet
177	Kahutsi	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Penannular brooches, tin mount	Viking Age – Middle Ages		A. Kula	

No / Site / Nr	Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
178	Kalju	C	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Burnt metal items (penannular brooches, dress pins, bracelets, pendant, chain holders, chains, separators, bells, belt fittings, bridle mounts, scale weights), pommel(?), spearheads, axe, rivets	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		R. Koit	
179	Kalju	F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Ornament fragments, rivets, iron items	Viking Age – Modern Period?		R. Koit	
180	Kargi	F	Saaremaa (Jämaja)	Penannular brooch, button	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages, Modern Period		Anonymous	H. Luik
181	Karida	C?, F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Coins, pendants, finger-rings, metal bead, small round brooches, belt fittings, pommel, scale weight, buttons, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Kallas	
182	Levala	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Coins, coin pendants, chain separator, bell, jewellery fragments (e.g. finger-ring, bracelet), iron item	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Kula	
183	Levala	C?	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Zoomorphic pendant, mounts, strap end, rectangular ornament link, ring	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
184	Liiva	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Lance head	Early Modern Period – Modern Period		V. Järvis	
185	Läägi	C?, F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins, dress pin fragment, brooch, finger-ring, pendants, beads, buckle, buttons, scale weight, tobacco pipe cleaner, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Kallas	H. Luik
186	Läägi	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Spearhead	Bronze Age		A. Kallas	K. Paavel
187	Läägi	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Knife sheath	Final Iron Age		J. Rahnel	R. Rammo
188	Mullutu	HS	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Silver coin fragments, penannular brooches, belt fittings, jewellery fragments (penannular brooches, chain holder), bridle bits, copper alloy ingot, metal items	Viking Age – Middle Ages		K. Laane	M. Mägi
189	Pöitse	F	Muhu	Flint flake	Early Modern Period		K. Tuul	
190	Rahniku	C?, F	Saaremaa (Püha)	Penannular brooches, bracelet, finger-ring, bell, jewellery fragments (brooches, bracelets), cross-guard(?), belt fittings, spur detail(?) nails, book clasp	Final Iron Age - Modern Period		A. Kallas	
191	Rahu	F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Coin, finger-ring, scale weight	Early Modern Period		R. Pärn	E. Russow

No / Site / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Findings / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
192	Suur-Rahula	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Coin pendant, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (e.g. cruciform pendant, penannular brooch, chain, mount), finger-rings, rectangular ornament links	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period		A. Kula	
193	Tammese	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coins, cruciform pendant, ornament fragment	Modern Period		Anonymous	
194	Tumala	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Spearhead	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		V. Järvis	
195	Ulje	F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Coins, coin pendants, equal-armed brooch, silver brooch, ornament links, buckle, scale weight, tobacco pipe cleaner, thimble, buttons	Roman Iron Age, Pre-Viking Age, Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Kallas	
196	Uuemõisa	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Coins, fragments of penannular brooches, ornament links, bell, mount, bridle boss, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		A. Kula	
197	Varpe	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Coin pendants, brooch(?), fragment of penannular brooch, needle(?)	Final Iron Age(?), Early Modern Period		K. Laane	
198	Vedruka	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Tweezers	Viking Age – Middle Ages		T. Tohv	H. Luik
TARTUMAA								
199	Ahunapalu (Leego)	S	Kastre (Võnnu)	Coin, coin pendant, cruciform pendant, finger-rings, small round brooch, mount, metal item	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	
200	Kukulinna	F	Tartu (Äksi)	Pendant	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
201	Kusma	F	Peipsiääre (Maarja-Magdaleena)	Bracelet fragments, belt fittings, bell, metal items	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		Anonymous	
202	Kuusiku	S	Peipsiääre (Maarja-Magdaleena)	Coins, cruciform pendants, small round brooch, finger-ring, spur detail, bell, mounts, buckle, book clasp, ring, buttons, metal items, wheel-thrown pottery sherd	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Smirnov	S. Jegorov
203	Lammiku	S	Tartu (Äksi)	Zoomorphic pendant, bead, lock cover, flint flakes and debris, quartz, ring, spoon handle, metal items	Mesolithic, Middle Ages – Modern Period		I. Kiudorf	
204	Lemmatsi	S?	Kambja (Tartu-Maarja)	Silver coin, coin pendant	Early Modern Period		A. Kovalev	
205	Lääniste	C, F	Kastre (Võnnu)	Penannular brooches, small round brooches, bracelets, signet finger-rings, finger-rings, belt fittings, buttons	Middle Ages – Modern Period		A. Kasemets	M. Kaseorg
206	Nina	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Cruciform pendants, finger-rings, mounts, buttons, ornament fragment, metal items	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Kotkin	

No / Site / Nr Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
207 Piiri	F	Tartu (Räpina)	Coins, coin pendants, cruciform pendants, finger-rings, heart-shaped brooch, round brooch, pewter mount, mounts, buttons, bridle details, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Kotkin	
208 Praaga	S	Peipsiääre (Võnnu)	Coins, signet finger-ring, buckle, knives, lock, bullets, metal item	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	
209 Pusi	H	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Silver coins	Viking Age		Anonymous	I. Leimus
210 Pühi	S	Kambja	Cruciform pendant, finger-rings, ornament fragment, ring, sickle, metal items	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		A. Kasemets	M. Kaseorg
211 Saare	F	Tartu (Räpina)	Coins, coin pendants, cruciform pendants, finger-rings, mounts, ear rings, ear spoons, ornament fragment, pendant, buttons, lock, bone item	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Kotkin	
212 Selgise	F	Peipsiääre (Maarja-Magdaleena)	Axe, spur, lock, lock cover, ox shoe, nails, sharpening stone	Early Modern Period		R. Otsa	R. Saage
213 Tooni	F	Tartu (Räpina)	Coins, cruciform pendants, signet finger-rings, ear spoon, mounts, buttons, metal items, wheel-thrown pottery	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	
214 Vara	C, F	Peipsiääre (Maarja-Magdaleena)	Coins, bracelet fragments, burnt metal items (e.g. penannular brooch), ornament link, finger-rings, belt fittings, bell	Viking Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
215 Varnja	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Coins, dress pins, bracelet, cruciform pendant, finger-ring, belt fittings, knife sheath detail, bells, buttons, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Kotkin	
216 Valguta	S	Elva (Rannu)	Silver coin, glass bead, iron items, wheel-thrown pottery	Viking Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	A. Lillak
VALGAMAA							
217 Jõgeveste	H	Tõrva (Helme)	Silver sheet pendants, silver and pewter beads	Early Modern Period	TÜ 2845	Anonymous	A. Tvauri
218 Lota	H, S	Valga (Sangaste)	Coins, neck ornament with coins, beads, bracelet, signet finger-ring, mounts, needle case, wheel-thrown pottery	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	
219 Priipalu	F	Valga (Sangaste)	Seal matrix, bell	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	
220 Uniküla	S	Valga (Sangaste)	Coins, coin pendant, round brooches, signet finger-rings, bells, mounts, book clasp, key, copper alloy pot, tobacco pipe fragment, metal items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	

No / Site / Nr Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
221 Uniküla	H	Valga (Sangaste)	Coins, silver beads, pewter vessel fragments	Early Modern Period		Anonymous	
222 Õruste	F	Valga (Sangaste)	Coins, coin pendants, penannular brooches, small round brooch of silver, stone spindle whorl, flint flake	Final Iron Age, Early Modern Period – Modern Period		Anonymous	

VILJANDIMAA

223 Karksi	F	Mulgi (Karksi)	Coins, bells, jewellery fragments (e.g. bracelet, signet finger-ring), lead seal, metal items (partly melted)	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	
224 Kerita	F	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Coins, bracelet fragments, penannular brooch, finger-rings, bells, brooch fragment, belt fittings, knife, metal items, melted copper alloy object, crampon	Middle Ages – Modern Period		J. Nugis	
225 Pöögle	C?	Mulgi (Karksi)	Spiral bracelet, fire-steel, spearheads, rings, metal items	Viking Age – Final Iron Age(?)		Anonymous	

VÕRUMAA

226 Kõlbi	C	Antsla (Urvaste)	Penannular brooches	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		J. Naaber	S. Jegorov
227 Oe	F	Antsla (Urvaste)	Cross-ribbed brooch, bracelet fragment	Roman Iron Age, Viking Age – Final Iron Age		J. Kiidron	
228 Popovitsa	F	Setomaa	Coins, finger-rings, pewter ornament, button, axe	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Kotkin	R. Rammo
229 Popovitsa	F	Setomaa	Cruciform pendant, axe	Middle Ages		Anonymous	

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OTSINGUVAHENDID, UUED AVASTUSED JA NENDEGA SEOTUD PROBLEEMID EESTI ARHEOLOOGIAS AASTAL 2020

Tuuli Kurisoo, Riina Rammo, Maria Smirnova ja Nele Kangert

Artikkel annab ülevaate 2020. a jooksul Muinsuskaitseametisse jõudnud otsinguvahendiga ja juhuslikult avastatud arheoloogilistest leidudest; lisaks käsitletakse hobiotsimisega seotud probleeme. Arheoloogiliste leidude ja leiukohtade ülevaade põhineb tabelis 1 esitatud informatsioonil. Seal on välja jäetud esemed, mida ei õnnestunud täpsemalt määrata ning leiukogumid, mis koosnevad 19.–20. saj leidudest. Artiklis kasutatakse Kriiska jt poolt üldteoses „Eesti ajalugu I“ (2020) avaldatud kronoloogiat.

Kõige arvukamalt on leiukohti teada põhjapoolsest Eestist – Harjumaalt, Ida- ja Lääne-Virumaalt, Raplamaalt ja Järvamaalt (tabel 1; jn 1). Eriti paistab silma Lääne-Virumaa, kust võrreldes varasemate aastatega anti üle palju rohkem leide, neist hulk on avastatud aastaid tagasi. Põhja-Eesti muististest saadi kõige rohkem teavet rauaaegsetest kalmetest (nt nr 3, 12, 17, 23, 30, 34, 57, 60, 122, 123, 128, 130, 136, 165, 171). Matusekohtade leidudest on Eesti kontekstis haruldane Mõdrikult pärit viikingiaegne ripats (jn 2), millel on paralleele nii Skandinaaviast kui ka Venemaalt. Kiia juba varem teadaolevalt kalmelt leiti tõenäoliselt rahvasterännuaega kuuluv hõbedast ja loomornamendiga sõlekatke (nr 12). Kahest tabelis märgitud mündiaardest üks pärineb viikingi- (nr 21) ja teine varauusajast (nr 136). Ehetest koosnevad peitleiud avastati Valingust (nr 49), Jägalast (nr 7) ja Maardust (nr 22). Viimasest pärinevad eriaegsed ehted võivad viidata ohverdamiskohale. Asulakohad on peamiselt dateeritud pikka perioodi muinasaja lõpust uusajani (nt nr 26, 100) või ainult uusaega (nt nr 39, 124). Nende leiumaterjal koosneb suures osas müntidest ja rõivaste detailidest, nagu nt pandlad, sõled või nõöbid.

Lisaks tuleb igal aastal ette ka mitmeid haruldasi juhuleide. Kõige märkimisväärsem avastus – kiviaja lõpust (4000–2000 eKr) pärit vasest talb – saadi Tallinnast (nr 43). See on ühtlasi kõige vanem Eestist leitud metallist ese (jn 3). Mitmetest vanema rauaaja esemetest on Eestis väheesindatud või unikaalsetest tüüpidest kaks eelrooma rauaaegset kirvest (nr 16, 33) ja hõbedast 5.–6. saj ambsõlg Vinnist (nr 149). Huvitav leid on ka Kullist avastatud (nr 15) nahkrihma jäänuse külge kinnitatud luunulakujuline ehe, milliseid kasutati eelkõige ripatsitena. Samuti on viimastel aastatel suurenenud soomepärase leidude osakaal, mille näiteks sobivad kaks võrdõlgset sõlge (nr 55, 152). Rauast kaubatoorikud ja töötisjäädid (nr 55, 62), mida küll täpselt dateerida ei saa, avardavad oluliselt teadmisi rauatöö ajaloo kohta. Uusaegsetest leidudest on eri-

line Kemba (nr 11) võimalik valjanaast, millel on kujutatud Karl XII monogrammi.

Läänepoolse Eesti – Läänemaa, Pärnumaa ja Saaremaa – leiukohtade arv on tagasihoidlik. Kõige rohkem infot tuli Saaremaalt. Vähem kui kolmandikku leiupaikadest saab seostada muististega. Viimaste hulgas domineerivad jällegi muinasaja lõpusajanditesse dateeritud põletusmatustega kalmed (nr 118, 174, 178, 181, 183, 185, 190). Vanim juhuleid on pronksiaegne odaots Läägilt (nr 186) – alles kümnes selline leid Eestist. Vanemate esemete hulka kuuluvad veel Rooma münt (nr 195), 4.7. saj nuga (nr 176) ja kaks hõbedast 5.–6. saj kaelavõru katket (nr 116). Leiud muutuvad tunduvalt arvukamaks alates muinasaja lõpusajanditest, mil domineerivad ehted ja rõivaste metallist detailid. Esile tõstmist väärib üks 7. saj sõlg Uljest (nr 195), mis võib pärineda Soomest. Tavapärase esemetüüpe hulgas paistavad silma muinasaja lõpust või keskajast pärinevad pintsetid (nr 198) Saaremaalt. Unikaalne on varauusaegne Puskust pärit arvatav valjanaast, millel on kujutatud irvitavat nägu (jn 4). Mündiaardeid on teada kaks (nr 156, 158), mõlemad dateeriti 16. sajandisse.

Lõunapoolse Eesti (Jõgeva, Viljandi, Põlva, Tartu, Valga ja Võru maakondade) leiumaterjali hulgas domineerivad asulakohtade leiud (nr 77, 78, 80, 93, 94, 97, 199, 202, 208, 210, 216, 221). Arvukalt on teada ka matmispaiku, mille hulgas on enim viikingiaegseid ja/või hillisrauaaegseid põletuskalmeid (nr 85, 86, 214). Keskaegseid ja varauusaegseid külakalmistuid leiti kaks (nr 205, 226). Jätkuvalt tuuakse MA-sse arvukalt Peipsi järve äärestest piirkondadest kogutud leide, esemeid kogutakse seal kaldalähedasest madalast veest (nr 155, 206, 207, 208, 211, 213, 228, 229). Neljast aardeleiuist üks sisaldas viikingiaegseid münte (nr 209) ja ülejäänud kolm varauusaegseid talurahvaeheteid (nt krõlle, rinnalehti ja müntidest kaelakeesid). Enamik loetletud asulakohtadest on kasutusel olnud pikka aega, hiljemalt keskajast kuni uusajani. Kõige varasemad asulakohad pärinevad kiviajast, millest annavad tunnistust tulekivist ja kvartsist leiud (nr 93, 203). Rõõmustav on tõdeda, et üha rohkem tunnevad metallidetektorit kasutavad hobiotsijad ära erinevast materjalist esemeid (nt tulekivi, luu) ja üleantud asjade hulgas esineb sagedamini keraamikat (nt nr 202, 213). Näiteks leiti Meerapalust keskaegne luust kamm (nr 154). Vanimad juhuleiud Lõuna-Eestist on kaks rooma rauaaegset ehet – sõrmus (nr 96) ja sõlg (nr 227). Arvukalt on noorema rauaaja leide, millest

Piilsi tuleraudripats (nr 91) on veidi erilisem, sest selliseid on Eestist teada vaid üksikuid. Keskaegsetest ja varauusaegsetest arvukatest piasjasjadest võib esile tõsta loomakujutistega kaunistatud naaste, mis tõenäoliselt ehtisid Novgorodist pärit nahkkotte (jn 5).

Arheoloogiliste leidude otsimine maastikul on jätkuvalt populaarne hobi, mis paneb proovile praeguseks väljakujunenud MA süsteemi, sest hobitsijate üleantud leidude hulk on kasvanud väga suureks. Eesti üheks eripäraks võrreldes muu Euroopaga on arheoloogide kaasamine otsinguvahendiga saadud leidude kultuuriväärtuse määramise protsessi. Kõikide esemete kohta kirjutab arheoloog eksperdihinnangu, mis sisaldab ka leiukoha analüüsi. Arheoloogide väike arv ja MA-sse toodud esemete suur hulk on tekitanud olukorra, kus tabelis nr 1 loetletud juhtudest jõuti vaid alla veerandile õigeaegselt tagasisidet anda. See võib olla üks põhjusi, miks mitmed riikliku kaitse all mitte olevad leiukohad on hobitsijate jätkuvas huviorbiidis. Selline korduv otsimine ei

ole seadusega keelatud, kuigi võib muistist oluliselt kahjustada. Siiski leidub ka olukordi, mil MA soovib teatud piirkondades, ka kaitsealuse mälestise läheduses, otsimas käia, et täpsustada muistise piire. Selline koostöö toimib ainult siis, kui hobitsija pöörab piisavalt suurt tähelepanu leidude dokumenteerimisele ning ei lähe kaevamisega liigselt hoogu.

Arheoloogilise pärandi parim kaitse on inimeste teadlikkus selle väärtusest ja eri huvirühmade siiras koostöösoov. Praegu kehtiv süsteem seda eesmärki alati ei toeta ja vaja on lahendusi, mis aitaksid seda saavutada. Üks ettepanek on tekitada põhjalike ja kohati teadusliku artikli mõõtu eksperdihinnangute kõrvale massmaterjali jaoks lühivormid, mis teeksid süsteemi kiiremaks. Samuti võiks laiendada ekspertide ringi, sh kaasata arvukamalt arheoloogia eriala tudengeid. Lootust annab ka suurenenud arheoloogide arv MA-s, mis lubab rohkem leiupaiku maastikul üle vaadata ja neid vajadusel kiiremini kaitse alla võtta.

*A Bronze Age spearhead from Läägi on Saaremaa island (no 186).
Pronksiaegne odaots Saaremaalt Läägilt (nr 186).
Photo / Foto: Kristiina Paavel*

